

Stiffened cellulose sandwich composites

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ABSTRACT

Pulp fibre foams are a potential alternative to porous polymers; however, their poor mechanical properties limit their application to packaging materials. We utilised the sandwich composite approach to produce panels (370 mm x 300 mm x 20 mm) comprising of pulp fibre foams and kraft liner papers to improve the mechanical properties of such foams. Two types of sandwich structures are produced: foam core sandwich panels and stiffened sandwich composites. The resulting sandwich structures materials have apparent densities ranging from 80 kg/m³ to 161 kg/m³. The mechanical properties are assessed in compression, three-point bending and double lap shear loading conditions. We show that pulp fibre foam sandwich structures possess significantly higher compression and flexural moduli and strengths when compared to pure pulp fibre foams. Stiffening the pulp fibre foam core further by incorporation of kraft liner paper stiffeners results in even higher mechanical, including lap shear, properties.

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1. Introduction

Cellular plastics (polymer foams) can be produced from virtually any polymer in any form with a range of properties that are determined by the polymer itself, porosity and foam structure (open vs. closed celled). Porous polymers are of interest because of their outstanding thermal and acoustic insulation properties, and their balance of density and mechanical properties [1–4]. Many polymer foams are cheap commodity materials [4–6]. Cellulose pulp fibre (Papira® and Fibrease®) foams have emerged as alternative thermal [7–9] and protective packaging material [10,11] with adequate mechanical properties and energy absorption behaviour [12,13]. Pulp fibre foams are commonly produced by frothing aqueous refined pulp fibre suspensions followed by draining and drying [14] adopting the process initially disclosed by Gatward and Radvan [15]. Aqueous pulp fibre froths are produced by introducing air by vigorous shearing into surfactant containing pulp fibre suspensions. The liquid pulp fibre froth is web formed and dried to produce non-woven fibrous webs including papers [15] and pulp fibre foams [16]. Prior to that, stable pulp fibre foams were observed during paper production but were deemed undesirable because they were difficult to eliminate [17].

The mechanical properties of pulp fibre foams depend on foam density (porosity) and fibre orientation within the fibre foam [17,18] but are generally inferior in compression when compared to common polymer foams, such as expanded polystyrene (EPS) with similar densities [19,20]. Wagner et al. [16] investigated the structure–property relationship of cellulose foams produced from bleached softwood kraft pulp with densities ranging from 60 kg/m³ to 130 kg/m³. EPS foams with densities of 64 kg/m³ and 80 kg/m³ have similar compression moduli of 17.3 MPa and 18.3 MPa, respectively; increasing the density of EPS further to 120 kg/m³ results in significantly higher compression moduli of 51.8 MPa [20]. Contrary, pulp fibre foams in that density range have only 0.5 to 4 % of the compression moduli of EPS [21]. Nevertheless, pulp fibre foams could be useful as protective layer in bicycle helmets [22]. The compression properties of pulp fibre foams have been improved by crosslinking pulp fibres using borate [23], chitosan and cationic polyacrylamide [24], as well as phytic acid [25] – discussed below; the added benefit of these crosslinking procedures was improved fire retardancy. Organosolv lignin [26] and glyoxal [27] have also been used to bind or crosslink pulp fibres in acidic environments resulting in improved compression strength and resilience. Pulp fibre foams were strengthened by incorporation of wood and hemp fibres of various length and refining degree; the hierarchical fibre distribution resulted in stiffer foams compared to those produced from a single type of pulp fibres [28]. Besides pulp fibres, nano- and microfibrillated cellulose have been a popular choice to produce a range of cellular materials [29], however, nanocellulose production is quite energy and water intensive [30] more so than pulp fibre production.

A simple approach to improve the properties of porous materials are sandwich composite structures, which comprise two thin, stiff face sheets (skins) bonded to a lightweight core material [31]. Sandwich composite structures attracted particular attention for their outstanding mechanical property to weight balance. Core materials can be lattice structures [32–35], e.g., honeycomb, truss, web, corrugated structures, or homogenous foam materials. Sandwich composite design aims at optimising stiffness-to-weight and strength-to-weight ratios, making such materials ideal for applications where weight is a penalty [34]. Straight-forward design examples of renewable sandwich composites use paper skins attached to the major surfaces of a thick balsa wood core [36] or glass fibre reinforced concrete cast on a pine wood fibre foam core [37]. The incorporation of paper-based cores, e.g. honeycombs [38], into sandwich composites allows to combine the renewable nature of paper with the mechanical properties of sandwich structures. Fu and Sadeghian [39] produced bio-based sandwich beams consisting of flax fibre reinforced biobased epoxy resin skins and a paper honeycomb filled with a synthetic spray foam as core material. Although paper/

cardboard honeycomb structures are known and used in sandwich materials, the sandwich approach to improve the mechanical properties of pulp fibre foams has yet to be explored. We hypothesize that integrating paper stiffeners into pulp fibre foam cores will lead to a substantial improvement in mechanical properties of the resulting sandwich materials with very little weight penalty, offering a viable alternative to traditional polymer foam cores.

We report cellulose sandwich structures comprising lightweight pulp fibre foam cores and kraft liner paper (KLP) skins, produced using a facile moulding approach, allowing for the incorporation of paper stiffeners into foam cores. Manufacturing and mechanical characterisation of stiffened pulp fibre foam core sandwich structures will be discussed. We show that lightweight sandwich structures featuring pulp fibre foam cores and paper skins exhibit competitive mechanical properties compared with previously reported bleached softwood kraft pulp fibre foams [21,22], eucalyptus pulp fibre foams [12], nano-fibrillated cellulose aerogels [21,28,39], expanded polystyrene [20], and expanded polypropylene [40].

2. Experimental section

2.1. Materials

Bleached softwood kraft pulp (BSKP) sheets comprising 85 % spruce, 10 % pine, and 5 % larch was kindly provided by Zellstoff Pöls AG (Austria) and kraft liner papers with grammages (areal weight) of 225 and 400 g/m² (gsm) by Smurfit Kappa Packaging GmbH (Austria). Sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS, ≥ 99 %) and sodium carboxymethylcellulose (NaCMC, M_w = 250000 Da) – used here as binder – were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. All the chemicals and materials were used as received.

2.2. Preparation of sandwich composites

Unrefined BSKP was dispersed in water following TAPPI standard T-200:m using a valley beater (FRANK-PTI GmbH); the suspended pulp fibres had an average length of 2.2 mm and a Shopper Riegler degree (SR[°]) of 12. The pulp fibre concentration in aqueous suspension was adjusted to 12 w/v%. NaCMC was dissolved in water (5 w/v%) to prepare a master batch of binder solution. The aq. NaCMC solution was mixed into the pulp suspension using a bench-top mixer (Kenwood Chef TITANIUM) equipped with a whisking head operated at a power of 200 W. SDS was added into the NaCMC / pulp suspension to reach a pulp fibre / NaCMC (binder) / SDS (foaming agent) ratio of 95: 4.5: 0.5 by dry weight. 1.57 L of aq. slurry of pulp / NaCMC / SDS was frothed using the bench-top mixer operated at an output power of 400 W to produce wet froths with a target volume of 2.5 L (Fig. 1a). Kraft liner paper skins with a grammage of 225 or 400 gsm were placed on a metal mesh resting at the bottom of a polyoxymethylene (POM) frame (370 x 300 x 20 mm). The 2.5 L wet foam was transferred into the POM mould. After filling the mould completely, a paper sheet of the same grammage as the bottom one was placed on top of the mould to cover the surface of the wet pulp fibre froth. A metal mesh was placed on top of the paper and fixed to the mould with screws (Fig. 1a). The wet pulp fibre froth was dried at 80 °C for 12 h; the dried sandwich composites with kraft liner paper of 225 gsm and 400 gsm were called C225 and C400, respectively.

2.3. Preparation of pulp foam cores with different densities

To produce pulp fibre foams with a foam density of 80 kg/m³, 141 g of wet pulp fibre froths were filled into a 100 mm x 100 mm x 20 mm POM mould covered with Teflon coated glass fibre mesh and dried using the same drying protocol. To produce pulp fibre foams with densities ≥ 160 kg/m³, 286 g, 358 g, and 465 g of slurry of pulp fibre / NaCMC (95: 4.5 by dry weight) was forced into the 100 mm x 100 mm x 20 mm POM mould (excessive water was squeezed out from the froth) and dried.

Fig. 1. Schematic illustration showing the manufacturing process of (a) pulp fibre foam sandwich composites, (b) stiffened pulp fibre foam sandwich composites, and (c) directions used to describe test specimens.

2.4. Preparation of stiffened sandwich composites

As-prepared C225 and C400 were cut into 20 x 20 x 370 mm rectangles. A thin layer of NaCMC solution (5 w/v%) was applied to the paper face sheets of the rectangles to glue them together, forming paper stiffeners in the pulp fibre foam core (Fig. 1b). Subsequently, NaCMC solution was applied to the major surfaces of the paper stiffened pulp fibre core to attach paper face sheets of identical grammage to the core (Fig. 1b). The stiffened sandwich composites were dried at 80 °C for 5 h and called SC225 and SC400, respectively.

2.5. Preparation of paper web sandwich structures

Two 400 gsm paper sheets were glued together using NaCMC; the double layered paper (800 gsm) was cut into 20 x 300 paper beams. 15 paper stripes were placed perpendicular to 400 gsm paper face sheet and held in place using a sliced SC400 beam (Fig. S1, ESI). The 800 gsm paper beams were glued onto the paper face sheet using a pulp fibre-NaCMC (90: 10 by dry weight) slurry. The paper beams could not be fixed to base face sheet paper when using only a NaCMC solution. The glue was dried at 80 °C for 5 h and a top skin was attached to the structure using the same procedure. The resulting paper web sandwich composite structures were called PWS400 and served as control.

2.6. Density and porosity of kraft liner papers, pulp fibre foams, and sandwich composites

The envelop densities ρ_e of kraft liner paper, pulp fibre foams, and sandwich composites were determined by dividing the sample mass m by its volume V . The volume of kraft liner paper was determined as the product of its area and thickness measured using a digital calliper:

$$\rho_e = \frac{m}{V} \quad (1)$$

Porosities ϕ of kraft liner paper, pulp fibre foams, and sandwich composites were determined from their respective densities ρ_e and cellulose density ($\rho_s = 1500 \text{ kg/m}^3$) [41]:

$$\phi = \left(1 - \frac{\rho_e}{\rho_s}\right) \times 100 \quad (2)$$

2.7. Network structure of kraft liner paper and pore size

The network structure and fibril dimensions of the kraft liner paper were determined using scanning electron microscopy (SEM) (Fig. S3 ESI) using a JEOL microscope (JCM-6000) operated at a voltage of 10 kV. The surface of the kraft liner paper was glued onto aluminum stubs using carbon tabs and gold-coated using a sputter coater (JEOL Fine Coater JFC-1200) for 30 s at 30 mA. The pore size and fibril diameter of at least 30 fibrils was determined and averaged using the software ImageJ [42] (Table S1 ESI).

2.8. Surface area of pulp fibre foams

The specific surface area of the pulp fibre foams was determined using inverse gas chromatography (Surface Energy Analyser, IGC-SEA, Surface Measurement Systems, UK). Approx. 350 mg of pulp fibre foam was packed into a silane-treated glass column with an inner diameter of 4 mm and length of 300 mm. Prior to each measurement, the specimen was conditioned for 1 h at 30 °C and 0 %RH then all experiments were carried out at the same temperature 30 °C but varying relative humidity 0, 25, 50 and 90 %RH, with carrier gas (He) flow rate

of 10 sccm. Methane was used as reference gas to determine the dead time. n-Octane was injected at a fractional surface coverage of $n/n_m = 0.1$ –1 to determine the specific surface area S_{BET} . The Brauner, Emmett and Teller method was used to reduce the data.

2.9. Moisture uptake of kraft liner paper and pulp fibre foams

The moisture uptake of kraft liner papers with grammages of 225 g/m² and 400 g/m² and pulp fibre was characterised using dynamic vapour sorption (DVS Intrinsic PLUS system, Surface Measurement Systems, UK). Water vapor uptake was monitored at 25 °C by measuring the change in mass when samples were exposed to a relative humidity (RH) cycle ranging from 0 % to 95 and back to 0 %, in increments from 0 %, 10 %, 20 %, 30 %, 40 %, 50 %, 60 %, 70 %, 80 %, 90 % and 95 % RH, with each humidity step maintained for 2 h. A sample mass of approximately 15 mg and a nitrogen flow rate of 200 sccm were used during the tests.

2.10. Quasi-static compression tests

Compression testing of pulp fibre foams and sandwich composites was performed following standard ISO 844. Tests were conducted using a universal dual-column test frame (Instron 5969, Instron, Germany) equipped with a 1 kN or 50 kN load cell. Test specimens were cut using a band saw (Proxxon MBS 240) into shapes with dimensions of 50 x 50 x 20 mm (z-direction) and 20 x 20 x 20 mm (y-direction). Specimens (moisture content of 5 %) tested in ambient environment were conditioned overnight at 23 °C and a relative humidity of 45 ± 9 % (test room environment). Specimens were also tested at a higher moisture content (8 %), which was achieved by conditioning them in a chamber for 48 h at 22 °C at a relative humidity of 72 ± 5 % (Fig. S2 ESI). The relative humidity of the chamber was controlled using a saturated NaCl solution [43]. The composites were loaded in y- (in-plane) and z- (out-of-plane) directions (Fig. 1c) at a rate of 2 mm/min. Stress–strain curves were recorded. The elastic modulus E_c was calculated from slope of the first linear region of the stress–strain curves (typically within the strain <10 %); the compressive strength σ_c was determined at the end of the first linear region. At least five specimens were tested for each sample.

2.11. Three-point-bending tests

Three-point bending tests were conducted using the same universal testing instrument equipped with a load cell of 50 kN following the standard ISO 1209–2. The 3-point bending geometry comprised a 30 mm half-cylindrical impactor and 30 mm two half-cylindrical supports. The specimens were cut using a band saw into rectangles with dimensions of 290 x 40 x 20 mm. The conditioned specimens were placed on the supports having a span length of 240 mm to give a span-to-thickness ratio of 12:1. Specimens were loaded at a rate of 20 mm/min with the impactor oriented in either x- or y-direction (Fig. 1c). For each material, at least five tests were conducted. The flexural stress σ_f and strain ϵ_f were calculated using Eqs. (3) and (4):

$$\sigma_f = \frac{3FS}{2bd^2} \quad (3)$$

$$\epsilon_f = \frac{6Dd}{d^2} \quad (4)$$

where b and d are the width and the thickness of specimen, respectively, S the support span length, and D the deflection at any applied load F . Flexural stress–strain curves were plotted using these data. The flexural modulus E_f was calculated from the slope of the first linear region (typically within a strain of <5 %). The flexural strength σ_f was the maximum stress reached prior to failure.

2.12. Tensile tests of the kraft liner paper

Tensile tests of kraft liner papers with grammages of 225 and 400 gsm were performed using the universal testing frame equipped with a 1 kN load cell. The papers were cut into dogbone specimens (1BA in EN ISO 527–2) with 5 mm parallel width and 75 mm overall length (Zwick ZCP 020 Manual Cutting Press, Zwick, Ulm, Germany). The gauge length was set to 25 mm. Tests were performed at 23 °C and relative humidity 40–55 % with a testing velocity of 1 mm/min. The actual strain was recorded using a video extensometer (Gig ProE, iMETRIUM, Bristol, UK). Young's moduli E_t were calculated from the slope of the linear elastic region of the stress – strain curve. The tensile strength σ_t was calculated from the maximum load and the cross-sectional area of the specimens.

2.13. Double-lap shear tests

Double-lap shear tests were performed using our universal testing frame equipped with a 50 kN following the standard ISO-1922. The test specimens consisted of two sandwich composites with dimensions of 250 x 50 x 20 mm glued to three parallel wooden panels with identical width. A block of wood is fixed to the top of the two outer panels serving as spacer. Three ruler strips were drawn on the side of each of the three supports to determine the relative displacement.

Test specimens were fixed to the testing machine by connecting the middle wood panel to the stationary bottom fixture, while the spacer and two wood panels were connected to the top (mobile) fixture. Specimens were pre-loaded to 2 N and tested at a rate of 20 mm/min; tests ended after a 95 % load drop was recorded. The strain was recorded using a video extensometer, which was used to monitor the displacement of the marks on the ruler strips. The mean shear strain γ was determined at 4 locations in the specimen as follows [44]:

$$\gamma = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^{n-4} \left(\frac{\Delta x_k}{z_0} \right)}{n} \quad (5)$$

where Δx is the displacement measured at the k^{th} point, z_0 the initial thickness of the specimen, and n the total number of measurement points. The shear modulus G was calculated from the linear elastic region of the shear stress – strain curve:

$$G = \frac{F/A}{\gamma} \quad (6)$$

where F is the measured load acting over an area A . The shear strength τ_s is the maximum shear stress.

3. Results and discussion

Pulp fibre foam cores with a density of 76 ± 8 kg/m³ and a porosity of 95 % (Table S2 ESI) were produced. The pulp fibre foam possessed elastic moduli of 0.23 ± 0.07 MPa and 2 ± 1 MPa and mean crush strengths of 20 ± 10 kPa and 100 ± 10 kPa in z- and y-directions, respectively, which compared favourably with data reported by Wagner and Biegler et al. [21]. Their anisotropic mechanical properties are attributed to the pulp fibre orientation within the bulk of the foam. In our previous work [21] we showed that pulp fibre foams were very anisotropic with most fibres oriented in the xy-plane, giving rise to a layered structure; fibres oriented in the loading (y-) direction support higher compression loads. The adhesion/connectivity between pulp fibres also influences the mechanical properties of pulp fibre foams. We used NaCMC as binder to improve fibre connectivity; connections between fibres result in a reduced surface area of the pulp fibre network. The surface area of pulp fibres was 0.94 m²/g while that of pulp fibre foams was 0.86 m²/g. Our finding agreed with previous reports [45] indicating that the use of binders resulted in improved mechanical properties of pulp fibre foams. In general, mechanical properties of

porous materials depend on their density making direct comparison difficult.

The sandwich composite approach is a simple and convenient route to improve the mechanical properties of pulp fibre foams. Sandwiching pulp fibre foam cores with a density of $76 \pm 8 \text{ kg/m}^3$ between two kraft liner paper skins with grammages of 225 and 400 gsm resulted in sandwich composites with higher overall densities of $106 \pm 10 \text{ kg/m}^3$ (C225) and $161 \pm 5 \text{ kg/m}^3$ (C400), respectively (Table 1). In z-direction the compression moduli and strengths of C225 and C400 sandwich structures increased insignificantly compared to pure pulp fibre foam cores (Table 1) because the compression deformation occurred within the foam core. The stress–strain curves of sandwich composites compressed in z-direction possessed no yield point (Fig. 2a); the linear elastic region progresses directly into the plateau region followed by densification occurring at compression strains $>60\%$.

Loading C225 and C400 in y-direction caused compression of the foam core and in-plane (z-direction) compression of the paper face sheets. Compression stress–strain curves of the sandwich composites C225 and C400 (Fig. 2a) started with a linear elastic region representing the elastic deformation of the composites followed by yielding prior to a sudden load drop occurring when face sheets buckle (and sometimes kink, (Fig. 2c, Video S1 and S2 in ESI for buckling and kinking, respectively)). With increasing compression strain the face sheets will either debond completely (Fig. 2c) or kink into the foam core with accompanied debonding (Fig. 2c curve C400 with kinks). When face sheets debond they lose their support function and thus the behaviour of the sandwich structure is dominated by the behaviour of the foam core, showing a similar plateau and densification region as sandwich structures tested in z-direction. However, when face sheets kink into the foam core they cause densification of the core resulting in smaller load drops prior to the plateau region. The elastic moduli of C225 and C400 were $13 \pm 5 \text{ MPa}$ and $20 \pm 5 \text{ MPa}$, respectively, significantly exceeding those of pulp fibre foam cores, due to the support provided by the paper face sheets. C225 and C400 had higher crush strengths $300 \pm 10 \text{ kPa}$ and $500 \pm 60 \text{ kPa}$, respectively, than pure pulp fibre foam cores ($20 \pm 10 \text{ kPa}$) or when tested in z-direction (Table 1).

We produced pulp fibre foams with densities ranging from 76 to 260

Table 1

Envelop densities ρ_e , average compression moduli E_c , mean crush strength $\bar{\sigma}_c$ of pulp fibre foams and sandwich composites tested in z- and y-direction at low (top table) and higher gravimetric moisture content $u = \frac{m_w}{m_d}$ (bottom table).

Sample ID $u = 5\%$	ρ_e [kg/ m^3]	z-direction		y-direction	
		E_c [MPa]	$\bar{\sigma}_c$ [kPa]	E_c [MPa]	$\bar{\sigma}_c$ [kPa]
Pulp fibre foam	76 ± 8	0.23 ± 0.07	20 ± 10	2 ± 1	100 ± 10
C225	106 ± 10	0.32 ± 0.09	20 ± 10	13 ± 5	300 ± 10
C400	123 ± 9	0.5 ± 0.1	30 ± 10	20 ± 5	500 ± 60
SC225	126 ± 5	12 ± 2	250 ± 60	76 ± 8	900 ± 160
SC400	161 ± 5	19 ± 2	400 ± 20	103 ± 26	1300 ± 250
Sample ID $u = 8\%$	ρ_f [kg/ m^3]	z-direction		y-direction	
		E_c [MPa]	$\bar{\sigma}_c$ [kPa]	E_c [MPa]	$\bar{\sigma}_c$ [kPa]
Pulp fibre foam	86 ± 8	0.23 ± 0.1	20 ± 4	1 ± 0.2	100 ± 30
W-C225	102 ± 5	0.18 ± 0.05	10 ± 4	9 ± 0.2	200 ± 40
W-C400	115 ± 8	0.15 ± 0.1	10 ± 1	12 ± 3	200 ± 50
W-SC225	127 ± 7	9 ± 2	250 ± 60	26 ± 13	400 ± 100
W-SC400	153 ± 6	12 ± 2	400 ± 70	44 ± 11	800 ± 100

kg/m^3 and subjected them to compression tests in y- and z-direction. These data served as baseline for comparison with the compression properties of sandwich structures. Pulp fibre foams possess anisotropic compression properties because of the formation of thin “skins” forming during drying and the preferential pulp fibre orientation in z-x direction within the foams [21]. We plotted the elastic moduli of pure pulp fibre foams and sandwich structures (S)C225 and (S)C400 as function of envelop density (Fig. 3). The compression moduli of the pure pulp fibre foams were fitted using the Gibson and Ashby power law [46,47] describing compression moduli E^* of open cell foams:

$$E^* = a \cdot (\rho_f)^b \quad (7)$$

where a is a material related factor, which was equal to 0.0032 and 4.9×10^{-5} in y- and z-direction, respectively, and b a structure related coefficient equal to 1.57 and 2.09 in y- and z-directions, respectively. a and b are close to the coefficients reported for open porous foams ($b = 2$) [45,46]. The fitted power law agreed with that previously reported for pulp fibre foams [21]. The moduli of the sandwich structures C225 and C400 determined in z-direction were of the same order as those of pure pulp fibre foams tested in the same direction and were described by the Gibson and Ashby power law, while those of C225 and C400 tested in y-direction significantly exceeded the Gibson-Ashby power law of the corresponding pulp fibre foams, clearly indicating the benefit of the sandwich composite approach (Fig. 3).

Under 3-point bending load, pulp fibre foams had a linear elastic region at strains <0.1 with flexural moduli of $29 \pm 5 \text{ MPa}$ (Table 2). Pulp fibre foams failed in tension on the bottom side of the specimens [21], resulting in flexural strengths of $0.3 \pm 0.1 \text{ MPa}$. After failure, the specimens gradually deformed because of the damaged fibre network. Sandwich composites C225 and C400 possessed significantly higher flexural moduli of $95 \pm 40 \text{ MPa}$ and $106 \pm 4 \text{ MPa}$, respectively, than pulp fibre foams (Fig. 4a and Table 2).

The higher moduli of the sandwich structures were caused by the stiffer kraft liner papers with a grammages of 225 and 400 gsm having tensile moduli of $2200 \pm 260 \text{ MPa}$ and $2455 \pm 230 \text{ MPa}$, respectively. Increasing bending loads deformed the kraft liner paper on the top side of the sandwich structure (Fig. 4b and Video S3, ESI), causing it to eventually fold at flexural stresses of approximately $0.7 \pm 0.1 \text{ MPa}$, which were only 2 times higher than those of pulp fibre foam cores. It is worth to notice that after the yield point of the sandwich structures, they were still able to carry much higher loads than the pulp fibre foams (Fig. 4a). This was due to fact that the bottom face sheet did not fail throughout the entire tests.

A well-established method to stiffen sandwich panels against compression and bending is the inclusion of stiffeners perpendicular to the face sheets into the foam core [48,49,50]. To improve the bending properties of cellulose-based sandwich structures, we compartmentalised the foam cores by incorporation of longitudinal kraft liner paper stiffeners. When loading SC225 and SC400 in compression in z-direction, they had much improved compression moduli as compared to C225 and C400 (Fig. 2b and Table 1), because the paper stiffeners provided additional support against compression loading identical to C225 and C400 when loaded in y-direction. After the yield point, accompanied by stiffener buckling (Video S4, ESI), the kraft liner paper stiffeners were compacted yet still provide some support against compression load as evidenced by a lower load drop after the yield point (Fig. 2b, Table 1) when compared to C225 and C400 (Fig. 2a) as well as paper cardboard with honeycomb core, which exhibited a stress drop from 0.16 MPa to 0.08 MPa [50]. Increasing the compression load on SC composites further densified the sandwich structures, resulting in an earlier onset of the densification range (strain of ~ 0.55) as compared to C225 and C400 (strain of ~ 0.7) (Fig. 2a).

When SC225 and SC400 were compressed in y-direction, they possessed compression moduli of $76 \pm 8 \text{ MPa}$ and $103 \pm 26 \text{ MPa}$, respectively, nearly 6 times higher than those of C225 and 5 times those

Fig. 2. (a) Representative compression stress–strain curves of pulp fibre foam cores / sandwich structures C225 and C400, (b) representative compression stress–strain curves of stiffened paper sandwich structures at $u = 5\%$, where the solid lines represent tests performed in z-direction and the short dash lines tests performed in y-direction, and (c) example compression stress–strain curves of C400 specimen with face sheet buckling and kinking.

of C400 loaded in y-direction. The improved rigidity of the sandwich composite was primarily caused by the fact that in this loading direction the stiffened composites contained two more (double grammage) paper stiffeners than C225 and C400 (Fig. 2). The paper stiffeners were orientated and bonded perpendicular to the two paper face sheets. The presence of the stiffener inside the foam core effectively delayed buckling/kinking of the paper face sheets. SC225 and SC400 had also much higher crush strengths of 900 ± 160 kPa and 1300 ± 250 kPa, respectively, as compared to C225 and C400 loaded in y-direction (Table 1). No face sheet debonding was observed in SC composites during compression loading in y-direction; instead, wall crushing was observed (Video S5, ESI). The compression moduli of stiffened sandwich composites were approximately two orders of magnitude higher as compared to pulp fibre foams with comparable densities in both y- and z-directions (Fig. 3).

Under 3-point bending load in y-direction (the impactor parallel to the stiffeners), SC225 and SC400 possessed flexural moduli of 80 ± 11 MPa and 142 ± 44 MPa, and flexural strengths of 0.9 ± 0.2 MPa and 1.3 ± 0.2 MPa, respectively, which did not significantly outperform C225 and C400 (Table 2 and Fig. 5a). The edges of the specimens remained perpendicular to the face sheets of the specimens during flexural testing (Fig. 5b), indicating that bending did not result in a shear deformation at the edges of the specimens. This observation is explained by the presence of the stiffeners in compartmentalised pulp fibre foams, preventing in-plane shear in the core. However, shear deformation was observed in the compartments near the impactor (evidenced by trapezoidal shaped compartments close to the impactor as compared to the rectangular compartments at the edges of the specimens, Fig. 5b). The local shear

caused face sheet debonding from the foam core in these compartments (Fig. 5b). Such debonding occurred in the very early stages during flexural tests, represented by peaks in the linear region of the stress–strain curves (Video S6, ESI).

When bending load was applied in x-direction, i.e. impactor perpendicular to the stiffeners, (Video S7, ESI), SC225 and SC400 had flexural moduli of 429 ± 38 MPa and 578 ± 79 MPa, and flexural strengths of 3.0 ± 0.2 MPa and 4.0 ± 0.3 MPa, respectively (Fig. 5a). The significantly higher moduli in x-direction were caused by the resistance against bending of the paper stiffeners oriented perpendicular to the loading direction (Fig. 5b and c). After the initial elastic linear region, the paper stiffener progressively buckled on the compression side of the specimen (Fig. 5a region a-c, and Fig. S5, ESI) followed by the sudden load drop (Fig. 5a, region c) occurring when the bottom face sheet and the bottom side of the stiffer failed in tension (Fig. S6, ESI). The failed specimens still carried some load accompanied by progressing tension failure of the stiffener.

To highlight the necessity of using stiffened pulp fibre foams as cores for all-cellulose sandwich composites, we compared the shear properties of pulp fibre foams, sandwich composites comprising only face sheets and stiffeners (devoid of foam), and SC400. Pulp fibre foam cores had shear moduli of 0.95 ± 0.2 MPa (Table 3). Shear loading caused a rapid failure of the pulp fibre network due to the loose bonding between pulp fibres, resulting in a shear strength of 0.02 ± 0.01 MPa at a shear strain of 0.01 (Fig. 6a). Sandwich composites comprising only paper stiffeners devoid of foam had a shear modulus of 0.4 ± 0.04 MPa. The empty space in the core allowed for a large shear deformation represented by a yield strain of 0.1 and yet, a shear strength of only 0.02 ± 0.002 MPa. The

Fig. 3. Average compression moduli with standard deviation of pulp fibre foam cores tested in z- (empty squares) and y-direction (filled squares); datapoints were fitted using the Gibson and Ashby power law. Compression moduli of sandwich composites and stiffened sandwich composites tested in z- (empty stars) and y-direction (filled stars) as function of their density.

Table 2

Envelop densities ρ_e , mean flexural moduli E_F and flexural strength $\bar{\sigma}_F$ of pulp fibre foams and sandwich composites loaded in x- and y-directions.

Sample ID	ρ_e [kg/m ³]	x-direction		y-direction	
		E_F [MPa]	$\bar{\sigma}_F$ [MPa]	E_F [MPa]	$\bar{\sigma}_F$ [MPa]
Pulp fibre foam	95 ± 12	29 ± 5	0.3 ± 0.1	—	—
C225	106 ± 4	95 ± 40	0.7 ± 0.1	—	—
C400	114 ± 8	106 ± 25	0.7 ± 0.1	—	—
SC225	128 ± 3	429 ± 38	3 ± 0.2	80 ± 11	0.9 ± 0.2
SC400	155 ± 6	578 ± 79	4 ± 0.3	142 ± 44	1.3 ± 0.2

shear loading caused the stiffeners to tilt and, eventually, detach from the face sheets (Fig. 6b). SC400 had improved shear resistance, characterised by shear moduli of 2 ± 1 MPa and shear strengths of 0.12 ± 0.01 MPa. This was due to the foam filled compartments delaying stiffener tilting and debonding (Fig. 6c). Our finding agreed with previous reports on synthetic sandwich composites, both experimental and modelling, showing that the inclusion of foam in web cores resulted in increased resistance against local instability [49,51,52].

The moisture uptake of pulp fibre foams and kraft liner papers was characterised. Dynamic vapour de/sorption isotherms of both materials were type II (Fig. 7a). At 95 % RH, the moisture content of the pulp fibre foam and kraft liner paper reached 15 % and 17 %, respectively, aligning with previously reported moisture content of cellulose [53].

The pulp fibre foams and (stiffened) sandwich composites were conditioned at 72 ± 5 % RH and subjected to compression testing to investigate the impact of moisture on the mechanical properties. The apparent density of the conditioned foams and composites did not change significantly, because the moisture uptake $u = \frac{m_w}{m_d} \approx 8\%$ of foams and composites was slightly higher than that at 45 % RH ($u \approx 5\%$). Despite the relatively low increased moisture content, all compression moduli and most of crush strengths decreased significantly (Table 1). It

Fig. 4. (a) Flexural stress–strain curves of the sandwich composites C225 and C400 and the pulp fibre foam core as a control. (b) Behaviour of C225 and C400 during the three-point bending measurements.

is well-known that moisture negatively affects the mechanical properties of paper products without a wet-strengthening agent [54] and reduces its specific surface area (Fig. 7b). When C225 and C400 were

a

b

c

Fig. 5. (a) Flexural stress–strain curves of the stiffened sandwich composites SC225 and SC400 and the pulp fibre foam cores as control. (b) Deformation of SC225 and SC400 during the three-point bending loaded in y-direction. (c) Deformation of SC225 and SC400 during the three-point bending loaded in x-direction.

compressed in y direction, the humidified face sheets buckled at lower loads (Video S8 ESI), thus providing less resistance. The humidified and weakened pulp fibre foam network were easier torn apart by the buckling face sheets. This finding held true for humidified SC225 and SC400 compressed in z-direction (Video S9 ESI). When humidified SC225 and SC400 were compressed in y-direction, the paper face sheets buckled and debonded from the pulp fibre foam (instead of the torn of the fibre network, Video S10 ESI). Submerging our sandwich composites in water led to their disintegration within 24 h, apart from the kraft liner paper,

which remained intact. This allows the constituents to be recycled (Fig. S8, Video S11 ESI).

The compression moduli of our (stiffened) sandwich composites, other cellulose (composite) foams reported in literature, and polymer foam references were plotted as function of their density (Fig. 8) to juxtapose their properties. The compression moduli of C225 and C400 in z-direction, i.e. compression mainly in the pulp fibre foam, were in the range of those reported for cellulose foams. If paper face sheets and stiffeners were introduced into our sandwich composites to resist

Table 3

Apparent densities ρ_e , average shear moduli G , and shear strength $\bar{\tau}_s$ of the pulp fibre foam cores, sandwich composites, and paper web sandwich composite devoid of pulp fibre foam (PWS400). The shear load was applied in the out-of-plane direction.

Sample ID	ρ_e [kg/m ³]	G [MPa]	$\bar{\tau}_s$ [MPa]
Pulp fibre foam	76 ± 8	0.95 ± 0.2	0.02 ± 0.01
PWS400	85 ± 6	0.36 ± 0.04	0.017 ± 0.002
SC400	155 ± 6	2.05 ± 1.35	0.12 ± 0.01

compression load, the specific compression moduli of our (stiffened) sandwich composites outperformed other cellulose foams by 5 times (Table S3). A further increase in the number of paper stiffeners in the stiffened composites boosted their moduli from ~20 MPa up to 105 MPa (Fig. 8), which was 30 times higher than those of other cellulose foams reported in literature and even higher than those of polystyrene and polypropylene foams. We stress that increasing the number of paper stiffeners brings only a small weight penalty, highlighting that producing (stiffened) sandwich composites is a suitable approach to produce light-weight cellulose materials.

4. Conclusion

Sandwich structures comprising pulp fibre foam cores and kraft liner paper face sheets, as well as paper stiffened sandwich composites were successfully produced using a straightforward and scalable process.

These sandwich composites exhibited anisotropic mechanical properties due to the presence of paper face sheets. While the out-of-plane (z-direction) compression moduli and strength remained comparable to those of the pulp fibre foams, in-plane (y-direction) compression moduli and strengths improved significantly, reaching 20 MPa and 500 kPa, respectively, representing six- and five-fold increases over simple pulp fibre foams. Flexural properties also increased because of resistance of the face sheets against deformation.

The introduction of paper stiffeners within the pulp fibre foam core resulted in even better mechanical properties. These stiffened sandwich composites outperformed simple sandwich structures in compression and provided much higher flexural moduli of 580 MPa, compared to 30 MPa for pulp fibre foams and 95 MPa for simple sandwich composites. Compartmentalizing the pulp fibre foam core resulted in much better resistance to shear deformation relative to both the foam core and empty web core configurations. As for all cellulose based products, moisture negatively affects the mechanical properties of our sandwich composites. These finding highlight that the sandwich approach is a promising strategy to develop lightweight, bio-based structural materials with enhanced mechanical properties with potential applications in packaging, construction and transportation.

Consent for publication

All authors approved the final manuscript and the submission to this journal.

Fig. 6. (a) Double lap shear stress–strain curves of stiffened sandwich composites SC400, pulp fibre foams, and sandwich composites comprising paper face sheets and stiffeners devoid of foam PWS400. (b) Sandwich composites comprising paper face sheets and stiffeners devoid of foam PWS400 prior to and after failure. (c). SC400 before and after failure.

Fig. 7. (a) Water sorption adsorption–desorption isotherms of pulp fibre foam, KLP225 and KLP400 obtained from DVS and (b) Variation of the specific surface area (S_{BET}), obtained from iGC, as a function of the relative humidity.

Fig. 8. Ashby plot of compression moduli as function of envelop density of our foams compared to literature values of pulp fibre foams as well as EPS [12,18,20,21,26,40,55,56,57,58]. Our data were obtained in by testing in both z- and y-direction.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Nesrine Battoul Debabèche: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Markus Wagner:** Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Qixiang Jiang:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Florian Feist:** Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Alexander Bismarck:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Ethics approval and consent to participate

(Not applicable).

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: All authors report financial support was provided by EU Framework Programme for Research and Innovation Future and Emerging Technologies. No known competing financial interests or personal relationships could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesa.2025.109080>.

Data availability

All data generated or analysed during this study are included in this published article.

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